

The Impact of Economic Sustainability on Improving Environmental Sustainability in Housing

Atiye Jarrahi , Ardalan Aflaki* , Mojgan khakpour

1. Master student of architecture, University of Guilan, Atiyejarrahi@msc.guilan.ac.ir
2. Assistant Professor of Art and Architecture, University of Guilan, Ar.Aflaki@guilan.ac.ir
3. Assistant Professor of Art and Architecture, University of Guilan, Khakpour@guilan.ac.ir

Abstract

This study examines the influence of economic sustainability on improving environmental sustainability in the housing sector. It aims to understand how economic factors can facilitate the implementation of environmentally friendly practices in housing construction and operation.

Initial findings suggest that economic sustainability measures, including energy-efficient design features and sustainable materials, can lead to significant reductions in energy consumption and operational costs over time. studies reveal that economic incentives, such as tax credits and grants for sustainable housing initiatives, play a crucial role in encouraging developers to prioritize environmental sustainability.

The study concludes that economic and environmental sustainability are interdependent in the housing sector. It highlights the need for policymakers to establish supportive frameworks that incentivize developers to adopt sustainable practices. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of raising awareness among stakeholders about the long-term economic benefits of investing in environmentally friendly housing.

The implications of this research are significant for both the housing industry and sustainability policymakers. By demonstrating the potential economic advantages of incorporating environmental sustainability measures into housing projects, this study advocates for increased investment in sustainable housing initiatives. It aims to shape policies that promote the integration of economic and environmental sustainability in the housing sector, leading to a more sustainable built environment.

Key words: Economic sustainability, Environmental sustainability, Housing, Construction, Energy consumption

1. Introduction

In recent years, the world has witnessed an increasing emphasis on sustainability to address the pressing challenges of rapid urbanization and climate change. As societies grapple with the consequences of their actions, it has become evident that a shift towards sustainable practices is not only necessary but also imperative for the well-being of future generations. This article aims to explore six key areas that are crucial in the pursuit of sustainability: economic sustainability, environmental sustainability, housing, construction, energy consumption, and policy incentives [1-5].

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Economic sustainability is a fundamental aspect of sustainable development. It encompasses the responsible management of resources, the promotion of fair-trade practices, and the creation of long-term economic growth that does not compromise the needs of future generations. By adopting sustainable economic practices, societies can ensure the preservation of natural resources and foster social equity [6-9].

Environmental sustainability is another vital component of the sustainability agenda. It involves the protection and conservation of ecosystems, biodiversity, and natural resources. As climate change continues to pose significant threats to our planet, it is essential to adopt measures that mitigate its impact and promote environmental stewardship. This includes reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting renewable energy sources, and implementing sustainable land-use practices [8, 10].

Housing and construction are critical areas that contribute to both economic and environmental sustainability. The construction industry has a significant impact on resource consumption, waste generation, and energy use. By adopting sustainable building practices, such as using eco-friendly materials, implementing energy-efficient designs, and incorporating renewable energy sources, we can minimize the environmental footprint of buildings and create healthier living spaces for inhabitants [6-8].

Energy consumption is a key area where sustainable practices can make a substantial difference. As the energy demand continues to rise, it is essential to transition from fossil fuel-based energy sources to renewable alternatives. This includes investing in solar, wind, and hydroelectric power, improving energy efficiency in buildings and transportation, and promoting the use of clean technologies [11-13].

Lastly, policy incentives play a crucial role in driving sustainable practices. Governments and regulatory bodies can provide financial incentives, tax breaks, and subsidies to encourage businesses and individuals to adopt sustainable practices. By creating a favorable policy environment, societies can accelerate the transition toward sustainability and foster innovation in various sectors [14].

In conclusion, the pursuit of sustainability is a global imperative that requires concerted efforts across various sectors. By focusing on economic sustainability, environmental sustainability, housing, construction, energy consumption, and policy incentives, we can create a better future for ourselves and future generations. Adopting sustainable practices not only benefits our communities but also ensures the long-term health and well-being of our planet.

2. Literature review

The relationship between economic sustainability and environmental sustainability in housing is complex and requires a balance between the two. While economic sustainability is important for the success of affordable housing projects, it is not sufficient to bridge the gap between sustainable housing and affordable housing [12]. The conventional ratio and residual approaches that focus solely on the economic issues of price affordability of housing do not consider the environmental and social sustainability of housing [15]. However, using energy-efficient technologies including passive design, the use of recycled and local materials, and

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socio-technical innovations, are effective in improving the sustainability of affordable housing. Therefore, it is essential to consider economic, social, cultural, and environmental sustainability when measuring the success of sustainable affordable housing projects. Studies have shown that sustainable design techniques, integrating environmental sustainability and social justice in housing development are also crucial to achieving an environmentally sustainable housing future [8, 12, 13, 15-17].

Numerous studies, such as the research conducted by Santamouris et al [18] and Givoni [19], have shown that incorporating economic sustainability measures into housing projects can significantly about 80% reduce energy consumption and improve environmental sustainability. These studies highlight the effectiveness of natural ventilation strategies, such as cross-ventilation and stack effect, in reducing cooling energy usage by up to 80% in residential buildings [9, 20-22].

Affordable housing projects require a comprehensive set of critical success criteria (CSC)¹ for assessing their sustainability. The CSC for mass housing projects, which include environmental impact, customer satisfaction, quality, and overall cost and time, could be appropriate for affordable housing projects based on the similarities between mass housing and affordable housing. However, the definitional difference between them suggests that the CSC for mass housing is not a comprehensive CSC for affordable housing projects [23].

Affordable housing is defined as housing that is reasonably adequate in standard and location for a lower or middle-income household and does not cost so much that such a household is unlikely to meet other basic living costs on a sustainable basis [24, 25]. The rule of thumb is that housing is affordable if low-income households spend less than 30% of their income on housing [1, 2]. Therefore, different CSCs may be required to assess the sustainability of affordable housing if mass housing projects do not meet the affordability criteria/requirements [25].

Studies have shown that sustainable design techniques, including passive design, the use of recycled and local materials, and socio-technical innovations, are effective in improving the sustainability of affordable housing [22, 25]. Integrating environmental sustainability and social justice in housing development is also crucial to achieving an environmentally sustainable housing future [1, 15]. In contrast to the much-heralded “trade-offs” between environmental quality, social equity, and economic development, studies suggest that the dense, diverse, and mixed-use urban form can promote economic sustainability and improve the quality of life for residents [1, 15].

The following CSCs are essential for improving the environmental sustainability of affordable housing projects:

Critical Success Criteria¹

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1. Energy efficiency CSC: This measures the energy efficiency of the affordable housing project. Energy-efficient technologies and environmentally friendly materials can reduce the consumption of scarce energy and other resources, making the project more environmentally sustainable [12, 15, 26].

2. Location affordability cost CSC: This measures the cost of transportation to and from the affordable housing project. By reducing transportation costs, the project can reduce pollution emissions (such as carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide), which improves environmental sustainability¹. In a study conducted by Isalou et [3]; it was found that suburban households spent about 57% of their income on housing and transportation which was significantly higher compared to the 45% of housing and transportation expenditure spent by households in the urban areas.

3. Quality-related CSC: This measures the quality of the affordable housing project. High-quality housing can reduce maintenance costs and increase the lifespan of the project, making it more environmentally sustainable [1, 24, 27, 28]. A study on Africa [29] shows that Green Affordable Housing (GAH), could reduce the risk of poverty for low and moderate-income individuals by providing affordable, durable, and environmentally sound housing that is not significantly more expensive to build and operate than traditional housing. By reducing the cost of living, GAH can help low and moderate-income households save money and improve their financial stability. Additionally, GAH can help break the cycle of generational poverty by providing occupants with a better sense of community and pride in owning or living in a superior home [30, 31]. The model also aims to be located close to public transportation and support a neighborhood that is healthy, walkable, and connected to the broader community and natural environment [29].

4. Cultural sustainability CSC: This measures the impact of the affordable housing project on the cultural heritage of the community in several ways. By preserving the cultural heritage of the community, the project can contribute to environmental sustainability [1, 15].

It is worth noting that cultural sustainability is an important aspect of sustainable development, and it involves preserving and promoting cultural diversity and heritage. In the context of affordable housing projects, cultural sustainability could be achieved by ensuring that the housing facilities are designed and implemented in a way that respects the cultural values and traditions of the communities they serve. This could include incorporating cultural elements into the design of the housing facilities, such as traditional building materials or architectural styles [11, 32]. By promoting cultural sustainability in affordable housing projects, policymakers, developers, and other stakeholders can help build stronger and more resilient communities that are better able to meet the needs of low-income households [33].

Six factors were developed for bridging the gap between sustainable housing and affordable housing: (1) household satisfaction CSC, (2) stakeholder's satisfaction CSC, (3) housing operation cost CSC, (4) time measurement CSC, (5) location affordability cost CSC, and (6) quality-related CSC [1, 10].

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Household satisfaction CSC: is a critical success criterion (CSC) for assessing the sustainability of affordable housing projects. Studies have shown that household satisfaction is influenced by various factors, including the quality of the housing, the location of the housing, and the affordability of the housing. High-quality housing that is reasonably adequate in standard and location, good access to public transportation, employment opportunities, community services, and affordability are all important factors in household satisfaction [1]. Household satisfaction is important for several reasons, including:

(A) Measuring the success of affordable housing projects: The satisfaction of the residents who live in affordable housing projects is a critical factor in measuring the success of these projects. High levels of household satisfaction indicate that the housing is meeting the needs of low-income households and is contributing to their overall well-being.

(B) Influencing subjective well-being: Studies have shown that household income and spending have a positive influence on satisfaction with the standard of living and subjective well-being. People who are satisfied with their family life and job experience higher well-being and happiness than those who are less satisfied.

(C) Affecting the quality of life: The quality of housing, its location, and affordability are all important factors in household satisfaction. High-quality housing that is reasonably adequate in standard and location, good access to public transportation, employment opportunities, community services, and affordability are all important factors in household satisfaction.

(D) Indicating the quality of healthcare services: Household satisfaction is an important indicator for measuring the quality of healthcare services. High levels of household satisfaction indicate that the healthcare services are meeting the needs of the households and contributing to their overall well-being.

On the other hand, investments in sustainable urban infrastructure such as bike paths and urban green spaces can result in rent and property value increases that often displace the low-income residents such projects were intended to benefit [34]. However, environmental gentrification is not an inevitable outcome of all urban sustainability initiatives that improve environmental quality in historically disenfranchised neighborhoods. Brownfield redevelopment in general, and new green spaces in particular, can be implemented without displacing long-term, working-class residents if planning processes are protective of locals' needs and demands [35-37]. Therefore, future planning efforts to build similar greenways should effectively engage affordable housing non-profits and dedicate specific funds for housing [38].

In conclusion, household satisfaction is an important factor in measuring the success of affordable housing projects and the overall well-being of low-income households [39]. It is influenced by various factors, including the quality of housing, its location, and affordability.

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Studies have shown that sustainable design techniques, including passive design, the use of recycled and local materials, and socio-technical innovations, are effective in improving the sustainability of affordable housing. Integrating environmental sustainability and social justice in housing development is also crucial to achieving an environmentally sustainable housing future [15]. In contrast to the much-heralded “trade-offs” between environmental quality, social equity, and economic development, studies suggest that the dense, diverse, and mixed-use urban form can promote economic sustainability and improve the quality of life for residents [12, 40].

3. Methodology

The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between economic sustainability and environmental sustainability in the housing sector. Specifically, we aim to investigate the impact of economic practices in housing development on resource consumption, waste generation, and greenhouse gas emissions. We conducted a comprehensive review of scientific literature, academic journals, and reports from reputable organizations to gather existing knowledge on the relationship between economic sustainability and environmental sustainability in the housing sector.

4. Result

The result of incorporating economic sustainability measures into housing projects is a range of positive impacts. These measures not only benefit the environment by reducing energy consumption and carbon emissions but also have significant social and economic benefits.

One of the key social impacts is the improvement in air quality, which directly contributes to the health and well-being of residents. By implementing natural ventilation strategies and reducing the use of fossil fuels, housing projects can create a healthier living environment, reducing the risk of respiratory problems and allergies.

Additionally, economic sustainability measures can promote social equity by making homeownership more affordable for low-income individuals and families. By reducing utility bills through energy-efficient designs and renewable energy sources, these measures alleviate financial burdens and improve access to sustainable housing options for marginalized communities.

Furthermore, the integration of economic sustainability measures creates job opportunities and stimulates local economies. The installation and maintenance of renewable energy systems require skilled workers, leading to employment opportunities in the green energy sector. This not only benefits the local economy but also contributes to overall economic growth.

overall, incorporating economic sustainability measures in housing projects is a win-win situation. It not only benefits the environment but also improves air quality, promotes social equity, and stimulates local economies. As we face the challenges of climate change and limited resources, prioritizing these measures in housing projects is essential for a sustainable and prosperous future.

5. Conclusion

The integration of economic sustainability principles in housing can have a profound impact on improving environmental sustainability. These improvements not only benefit the environment but also enhance the quality of life for residents.

However, challenges such as initial investment costs and lack of awareness among stakeholders need to be addressed for the widespread adoption of economic sustainability practices in housing. Governments and policymakers can play a crucial role in incentivizing and promoting these practices through financial incentives, tax breaks, and stricter building codes. Additionally, raising awareness among homeowners, developers, and construction professionals about the long-term benefits of economic sustainability can encourage their adoption.

Future research should focus on exploring innovative financing models and policy frameworks to promote economic sustainability in the housing sector. This includes investigating the potential of public-private partnerships, green bonds, and other mechanisms to facilitate the transition towards more sustainable housing practices. By addressing these challenges and conducting further research, we can pave the way for a more sustainable and environmentally friendly housing sector.

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